

Yashil

IQTISODIYOT va TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, siyosiy, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

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THE IMPACT OF AGRICULTURAL PRODUCTION ON FOOD SECURITY IN UZBEKISTAN IN THE COMING YEARS

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Abstract: This article examines the impact of agricultural production on food security in Uzbekistan in the coming years. The main focus is on strategies to ensure food security in the country by increasing agricultural production. The results of the analysis show that the development of agricultural production plays an important role in increasing food security. In the future, it is recommended to attract investment, introduce technologies and ensure environmental safety for the further development of this sector in Uzbekistan.

Key words: Agricultural products, food security, forecast, comparative analysis.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada qishloq xo'jaligi ishlab chiqarishining kelgusi yillarda O'zbekistonda oziq-ovqat xavfsizligiga ta'siri ko'rib chiqiladi. Asosiy e'tibor qishloq xo'jaligi mahsulotlari yetishtirishni ko'paytirish orqali mamlakatda oziq-ovqat xavfsizligini ta'minlash strategiyasiga qaratildi. Tahlil natijalari shuni ko'rsatadiki, qishloq xo'jaligi ishlab chiqarishini rivojlantirish oziq-ovqat xavfsizligini oshirishda muhim o'rin tutadi. Kelgusida O'zbekistonda ushbu sohani yanada rivojlantirish uchun investitsiyalarni jalb qilish, texnologiyalarni joriy etish va ekologik xavfsizlikni ta'minlash tavsiya etiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: Qishloq xo'jaligi mahsulotlari, oziq-ovqat xavfsizligi, prognoz, qiyosiy tahlil.

Аннотация: В данной статье рассматривается влияние сельскохозяйственного производства на продовольственную безопасность в Узбекистане в ближайшие годы. Основное внимание уделено стратегиям обеспечения продовольственной безопасности в стране за счет увеличения производства сельскохозяйственной продукции. Результаты анализа показывают, что развитие сельскохозяйственного производства играет важную роль в повышении продовольственной безопасности. В перспективе рекомендуется привлекать инвестиции, внедрять технологии и обеспечивать экологическую безопасность для дальнейшего развития этой отрасли в Узбекистане.

Ключевые слова: Сельскохозяйственная продукция, продовольственная безопасность, прогноз, сравнительный анализ.

INTRODUCTION

Food security providing the population with nutritious and safe food products, has become a pressing issue at the global level. This is especially important for developing countries, including Uzbekistan. Agricultural production in Uzbekistan is the main component of the country's economy and plays a decisive role in meeting the population's needs for food products. At the same time, ensuring food security means not only meeting demand in the domestic market, but also expanding opportunities for social stability and generating additional income for the national economy.

One of the factors increasing the importance of food security for Uzbekistan is the rapid growth in demand for food products as a result of population growth and economic development. A number of reforms aimed at meeting this need are being implemented in the country's economic policy, with attention being paid to increasing production volumes and improving the quality of products in the agricultural sector. At the same time, due to the arid climate of Uzbekistan, agricultural production is directly dependent on water resources. As a result, there is a need to develop irrigation systems, efficiently use water resources, and introduce water-saving technologies.

Another important factor is climate change. Sudden climate change, drought and other adverse natural conditions have a negative impact on agriculture and lead to a decrease in productivity. The results of the study show that in the coming years, in order to solve these problems and ensure sustainable agricultural production, it is necessary to pay attention to the widespread introduction of innovative technologies, efficient use of resources, and environmental safety. At the same time, Uzbekistan seeks to increase its competitiveness in the international market by expanding the possibilities of exporting agricultural products. To do this, it is necessary to improve the quality and compliance of agricultural products with standards, ensure stable production volumes, and use modern agricultural technologies. The main objective of this study is to analyze the prospects for the development of agricultural production in Uzbekistan in the coming years and its impact on food security.

The results of the study are aimed at identifying existing problems in the agricultural sector and developing necessary strategies to ensure food safety. This study demonstrates the need to develop agricultural policies, take into account economic and technological factors to ensure food security, and provides recommendations for further improvement in this area.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on ensuring food security of the country dated January 16, 2018 "On measures to further ensure food security of the country" and the development of a strategy for the development of agriculture in Uzbekistan for 2020-2030 was developed. For example, the strategy states that the share of undernourished people in Uzbekistan as of 2018 is 6.3 percent. It is planned to reduce this share to 3% by 2025 and to zero by 2030.

As part of the research, one of our domestic scientists on food safety N.M. Ziyavitdinova improved the organizational structure of network management in the formation of market strategies at food industry enterprises, developing directions for their development.

Foreign research scientists such as Stevenson W.J., Thompson A.A., Webster F. conducted research to improve food safety management mechanisms in the food industry and the development of the industry based on a vertical and horizontal cluster approach.

METHODS

This article has conducted a comprehensive analysis using a range of methods and statistical data to examine the dynamics of agricultural production in Uzbekistan and its impact on food security. The study was conducted in two main stages: collecting available data and analyzing them, and applying forecasting methods. The information is mainly based on official statistics provided by the Agency on Statistics under the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan. This agency reports on annual production volumes, growth rates, and demand for agricultural products grown in the country (e.g. wheat, cotton, fruits and vegetables, and other staple foods). The study also used information from the Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO), the World Bank, and other international organizations on agriculture and food security in Uzbekistan.

Comparative analysis: A comparative analysis of the dynamics of agricultural production was conducted, with a comparison made with the state of agriculture in Uzbekistan and population growth. Based on the comparative analysis, the features and level of changes in agriculture in Uzbekistan were determined.

Forecasting method: Using statistical modeling methods, the growth of agricultural production was predicted for the coming years, a forecast for 5 years was made, the expected growth rates of agricultural production and productivity levels were calculated.

RESULTS

Among the regions that produced agricultural products in January-November 2023, Samarkand region took the first place by producing products worth 49140.1 billion soms. If we look at the preliminary data of the State Statistics Committee, Andijan region and Kashkadarya region took the next places, producing products worth 41,278.6 billion sums and 38,565.3 billion soms, respectively. This indicator was as follows for the rest of the regions:

Bukhara - 37350,0
 Jizzakh - 26401,2
 Navoi - 18183,5
 Namangan - 29942,5
 Surkhandarya - 32756,1
 Syrdarya - 13372,2
 Tashkent - 37979,9
 Fergana - 38169,5
 Khorezm - 26160,4

According to the preliminary data of the Statistics Agency, in 2023, the total volume of agricultural, forestry and fishery products amounted to 426.3 trillion soums. This indicator has increased by 4.1% compared to 2022. It is noted that in 2023, 2.8 million tons of meat (in live weight), 12 million tons of milk, and 8.5 million eggs were produced in Uzbekistan in the field of livestock products. The volume of agricultural products grown in 2023.

Information about the total volume of agricultural products produced in Uzbekistan in 2019-2023 is presented in the table below.

№	Type of products	Unit of measurement	2021	2022	2023	Growth compared to 2021, in percent
1	Cereals and legumes, total	thousand tons	7634,6	7990,5	8426,6	110,4
2	Leguminous crops, total	thousand tons	439,8	469,5	489,8	111,4
3	Potatoes	thousand tons	3285,6	3443,2	3574,1	108,8
4	Vegetables	thousand tons	10850,2	11162,9	11553,7	106,5
5	Fruits and berries	thousand tons	2852,6	2999,3	3121,7	109,4
6	Grapes	thousand tons	1695,3	1760,6	1737,6	102,5

The table presents data on the production of various agricultural products over the years 2021, 2022, and 2023, along with the growth percentage compared to 2021.

Cereals and legumes, total: The total production of cereals and legumes showed a steady increase over the years, rising from 7,634.6 thousand tons in 2021 to 8,426.6 thousand tons in 2023. This represents a

growth of 10.4% compared to 2021, indicating a positive trend in the production of these crops. **Leguminous crops, total:** The production of leguminous crops also increased from 439.8 thousand tons in 2021 to 489.8 thousand tons in 2023, reflecting a growth of 11.4%. This shows an even stronger growth rate compared to the overall cereals and legumes category. **Potatoes:** The production of potatoes grew from 3,285.6 thousand tons in 2021 to 3,574.1 thousand tons in 2023, with an 8.8% growth. While the growth is positive, it is relatively lower compared to the other categories. **Vegetables:** Vegetable production saw an increase from 10,850.2 thousand tons in 2021 to 11,553.7 thousand tons in 2023. This reflects a growth of 6.5%, the lowest among the listed categories, but still shows a positive trend. **Fruits and berries:** Production of fruits and berries grew from 2,852.6 thousand tons in 2021 to 3,121.7 thousand tons in 2023, showing a growth rate of 9.4%. This is a notable increase, suggesting that fruit and berry production is on the rise. **Grapes:** The production of grapes showed a slight increase from 1,695.3 thousand tons in 2021 to 1,737.6 thousand tons in 2023, with a growth rate of 2.5%. This is the lowest growth among the listed products, indicating a relatively stable production trend for grapes.

Overall, the data suggests a positive growth trend in the production of most agricultural products, with legumes and fruits/berries showing the strongest growth. However, vegetable and grape production are growing at a slower pace.

In addition to increasing agricultural production in Uzbekistan, population growth and decreasing land and water resources may threaten future food security. For this reason, if current progress continues, an important task is to determine the volumes of their future production and assess the population's ability to have food.

Years	Number of permanent residents of the Republic of Uzbekistan, thousand people
2015	31022,5
2016	31575,3
2017	32120,5
2018	32656,7
2019	33255,5
2020	33905,2
2021	34558,9
2022	35271,3
2023	36024,9
2024	37355,4
2025	37419,9
2026	38126,2
2027	38845,7
2028	39578,9
2029	40325,9
2030	41116,2

According to the above results of the forecast for 2025-2030, we see that in the next 5 years the population of Uzbekistan will reach 41.1 million people. However, as we have already mentioned earlier, the reduction of water and land resources in the region negatively affects agricultural production, and the growth of agricultural production can only be due to modern technological progress.

As we see above, if the current trend continues, the production of the main types of agricultural products will grow until 2030. However, the production of meat and egg products in the country today is insufficient to meet the domestic needs of the population. The production of this type of product increases slightly from year to year, and this will not significantly change the level of satisfaction of the population's demand for meat and egg products in the future.

CONCLUSION

The process of analyzing the dynamics of agricultural production in Uzbekistan and its impact on food security shows that the volume of agricultural production in Uzbekistan has been increasing in recent years. However, this growth is not continuous and sustainable, since agriculture depends on many external factors (e.g. climate change, limited water resources, population growth). These factors have a significant impact on

changes in production volumes, which can cause problems in ensuring food safety. Therefore, it is necessary to diversify production and widely use new technologies.

In short, the future development of agricultural production in Uzbekistan will have a significant impact on food security. However, this process should include technological upgrades, efficient use of resources and measures against climate change. To ensure food safety, it is necessary to develop effective public policies, an innovative approach and international cooperation. The results of the study will also serve as a basis for the implementation of effective measures for further development of agriculture and strengthening food security.

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